

Investigations on Zinc Electrode with Reference to Leclanche Dry Cells

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The paper reports the experimental results on the anodic polarisation behaviour of commercial zinc in different concentrations of ammonium chloride ranging from 0.5–6.0 *N*, over a wide range of current density of 5–1000 mA cm⁻². The purity of the commercial zinc is determined as 99.972%. It is found that any concentration between 2 and 5.5 *N* of ammonium chloride can be suitable for use in zinc cells but the most optimum concentration is 5.5 *N*, at which the anode potential and the internal resistance of the electrode system are minimum. The corrosion rate of commercial zinc in 5.5 *N* ammonium chloride is determined for the constant time by conventional weight loss method. Typical scanning electron microscopic photographs of the polarised electrode surface are compared with the one obtained with unpolarised surface

Leclanche dry cells still continue to be an important commercial component in the battery world^{1,2}. The cell consists of zinc as the anode, manganese dioxide as the cathodic depolariser mixed with conducting materials and the carbon rod as the current collector. The electrolyte used in the original cell was an aqueous ammonium chloride in the gel form. McMurdie³ investigated zinc in ammonium chloride and reported the formation of prismatic crystals of Zn(NH₃)₂Cl₂ and small hexagonal plates of ZnCl₂·4 Zn(OH)₂ in the pastes of aged cells. Cahoon⁴ mentioned the occurrence of Zn(NH₃)₄Cl₂ at a pH of ~8 in addition to Zn(NH₃)₂Cl₂. There has therefore been a necessity to improve the status of technology in this area. Although good amount of work has been done in the past on zinc and its alloys used in Leclanche cells^{5,6}, not much information is available on the anodic polarisation behaviour of zinc in different concentrations of ammonium chloride electrolyte over a wide range of discharge currents, etc.

The present paper reports the results of polarisation studies made on zinc electrode under different experimental conditions. Zinc sample used in the experiments is analysed for its composition by atomic absorption spectrophotometer, with a view to understand the influence of the impurities on the performance behaviour of the anode. Scanning electron microscopic images are taken for a typical experiment, to understand the structural changes that occur on the electrode surface after polarisation. Corrosion behaviour of the electrode is also studied in a typical concentration of the electrolyte, and the corrosion rate is calculated after suitably cleaning the corrosion products.

Results and Discussion

Anodic polarisation of zinc in different concentrations of ammonium chloride: Figs. 1 and 2 represent

the anode potential vs current density curves for commercial zinc in 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 5.5 and 6.0 *N* ammonium chloride solutions. The OCP data of zinc in all concentrations of the electrolyte are given in Table 1. The electrodes are polarised from the rest potential by impressing the currents in the range 5–1000 mA and the corresponding values of potential are plotted in the figures. In 0.5 *N* ammonium chloride solution, however, erroneous results are recorded beyond 783 mA cm⁻² which is probably due to the rapid dissolution of the metal and oxygen evolution in the higher current density range. The internal resistance is calculated as tangent of the slope of the straight line curve. The comparative data of the internal resistance of zinc in different concentrations of ammonium chloride at different current density ranges are

Fig. 1. Electrode potential vs current density curves for zinc in (○) 0.5 and (●) 1.0 *N* NH₄Cl.

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Fig. 2. Electrode potential vs current density curves for zinc in different concentrations of NH_4Cl : (○) 2.0, (●) 3.0, (△) 4.0, (▲) 5.0, (□) 5.5 and (■) 6.0 N.

TABLE 1—OCP OF ZINC IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF AMMONIUM CHLORIDE

Concn. NH_4Cl N	Potential V (vs SCE)
0.5	-1.070
1.0	-1.072
2.0	-1.075
3.0	-1.093
4.0	-1.100
5.0	-1.110
5.5	-1.110
6.0	-1.110

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE DATA OF INTERNAL RESISTANCE OF ZINC IN DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF AMMONIUM CHLORIDE AT DIFFERENT CURRENT DENSITIES

Concn. NH_4Cl N	Current density mA cm^{-2}	Internal resistance, $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$
0.5	5-219	3.16
	315-780	4.21
1.0	5-360	1.30
	486-1000	2.13
2.0	5-357	1.00
	645-1000	1.52
3.0	5-609	0.93
	645-1000	1.32
4.0	5-609	0.83
	609-1000	0.95
5.0	5-1000	0.76
5.3	5-1000	0.59
5.5	5-1000	0.56
5.7	5-480	0.61
	630-1000	0.71
6.0	5-423	0.69
	735-1000	0.77

provided in Table 2. The internal resistance values are calculated for one or two ranges of the

current density, as the case may be. It may be noticed from the graphs that the internal resistance increases in the upper current density range. Also the trend of the change of the internal resistance of the electrodes is in decreasing order with the rise in concentration of the electrolyte up to 5.5 N, beyond which the resistance is increased. Internal resistance, however, falls sharply up to 2 N concentration, then decreases gradually with the increase in the concentration (Fig. 3). This nature of the graph obtained at the lower current density range of 5-219 mA cm^{-2} , follows same pattern in the upper current density range also and so it is not presented graphically for brevity.

Fig. 3. Dependence of internal resistance of zinc with electrolyte concentration.

It may also be noted from the potential vs concentration curve (Fig. 4) that the electrode potential of zinc decreases gradually with increase in the concentration of ammonium chloride from 0.5-5.5 N almost in the same way as internal resistance. At 6 N concentration, the electrode potential shifts to more positive value (Table 3). The graph (Fig. 4) corresponds to a constant current density of 645 mA cm^{-2} . These results are indicative of the fact that the optimum concentration of ammonium chloride solution for the polarisation of the zinc is 5.5 N and the polarisation of the electrode is

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF ELECTRODE POTENTIAL AGAINST THE CONCENTRATION OF ELECTROLYTE AT A CONSTANT CURRENT DENSITY OF 645 mA cm^{-2}

Electrolyte concn. (N)	Potential, V (vs SCE) Zinc
0.5	+1.48
1.0	+0.03
2.0	-0.24
3.0	-0.43
4.0	-0.52
5.0	-0.58
5.3	-0.69
5.5	-0.71
5.7	-0.68
6.0	-0.65

Fig. 4. Dependence of electrode potential with electrolyte concentration for zinc at a constant current density of 645 mA cm^{-2} .

very high in the electrolyte concentrations range below 2 N.

The curves in Fig. 3 (or 4) thus exhibit a break at the end indicating the descending order of the polarisation of the electrode from 0.5–5.5 N ammonium chloride solution which suddenly increases in the range 5.5–6.0 N and above. This deviation shows that some physical changes have occurred in the ammonium chloride solution resulting in the increase of the resistance of the electrode/electrolyte system. Separate experiments are carried out on the point of crystallisation of salts from the ammonium chloride liquor and it is experimentally found that ammonium chloride exists in solution phase up to a concentration of 5.5 N. Beyond this critical concentration, white crystals of ammonium chloride are formed from the solution, more with the increasing concentrations of the solutions prepared at 50–60°. The results on the crystallisation experiments clearly explain the causes of the break in the curves in terms of the minimum polarisation observed at 5.5 N ammonium chloride solution, i.e. beyond 5.5 N concentration, the ohmic resistance of the system is perhaps increased due to the crystal build-up.

Analysis of commercially pure zinc by atomic absorption spectrophotometer: The analysis results of commercially pure zinc obtained from atomic absorption spectrophotometer are : Cu, 0.005 ; Ni, 0.0 ; Sb, 0.0 ; Pb, 0.016 ; Fe, 0.005 ; Cd, 0.002%. The purity of the commercial zinc is thus found to be 99.972% which is within the requisite values for dry cell applications. The literature values⁷ for high

grade and special high grade zinc are 99.900 and 99.999% respectively.

Results of pre-polarised and post-polarised electrodes of commercially pure zinc obtained by scanning electron microscope: In these investigations, 1 cm^2 area of commercially pure zinc are exposed to SEM before polarisation and after polarisation in a typical concentration, i.e. 5.5 N of ammonium chloride, to get an idea about the occurrence of structural changes on the surface of the electrodes (Fig. 5).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. SEM pictures of zinc electrodes: (a) pre-polarised and (b) post-polarised.

In the polarised electrode, the grain boundaries attack appears to be taking place in the polycrystalline pure zinc electrodes and also latter inside the grains. The oxide pattern in the photograph 2711 also reveals similar features. This being a pure metal, probability of a single phase alone may be

there so that attack takes place preferentially on more anodic area at both grain boundary and inside the grain. Pits seem to be appearing in this case.

Corrosion rate for commercially pure zinc: The corrosion rate for zinc is obtained as 49.66 mpy. The half-cell potential readings for zinc were noted daily at the interval of 24 h and the potential of the electrode was found more or less unaffected even after 410 h. These studies are to be further continued for a longer period in order to get deeper understanding of the dependence of OCP with time.

The polarisation studies indicated that the commercial zinc having purity of 99.972%, is highly polarised below 2*N* concentration of ammonium chloride and least polarised at 5.5 *N* concentration. Beyond 5.5 *N* concentration of the electrolyte, again polarisation tends to be enhanced. It may be concluded from the results that any concentration between 2.0 *N* and 5.5 *N* ammonium chloride, can be suitable for use in zinc cells but the most optimum concentration is around 5.5 *N*, at which the polarisation potential and the internal resistance of the electrode system are minimum. SEM photograph of the post-polarised electrode surface when compared with the photograph of unpolarised electrode surface, reveals greater attack on the grain boundaries of the metallic structure.

Experimental

Zinc electrodes (1 cm²) were cut from the zinc metal (commercial grade) sheets of 0.5 mm thickness and were used as anodes. One side of these electrodes was masked by photoresist lacquer to enable the 1 cm² area alone to be exposed for the experiment. The test electrodes were polished with emery papers and degreased with acetone. After mechanical polishing, the electrodes were washed with double-distilled water. Copper wire leads were provided to the top ends of the zinc electrodes by soldering, followed by fixing the outer cover of hollow glass tubes.

Platinum foil (4.9 cm × 2.1 cm) was used as the auxiliary electrode and the saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrodes.

All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Aqueous solutions of ammonium chloride (B.D.H., L.R.) of concentrations 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 5.3, 5.5, 5.7 and 6.0 were prepared. Higher concentrations of ammonium chloride solutions, viz. 5.5, 5.7, and 6.0 *N*, were prepared by heating the solutions upto 50–60° with continuous stirring. The solutions were allowed to cool to room temperature (30 ± 2°).

Zinc solution of 1 gpl was made by dissolving the sample in 50% HCl (A.R., 1 ml) and then suitably diluted with double-distilled water. The solution was analysed for its composition by a Perkin-Elmer 380 atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Working electrodes and the platinum electrodes were immersed in a glass cell (100 ml) carrying the electrolyte solution (80 ml) in each experiment. These two electrodes were placed 4 cm apart in the cell. The distance between the working and the reference electrodes was kept very close to each other to minimise the *ir* drop. A Zenith ZE 1500 multimeter was used for the measurement of electrode potentials, and the current recordings were done with a ROMTEK ammeter. No potential corrections were made for liquid junction potential. The experimental galvanostatic set-up is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Experimental set-up.

All the polarisation experiments were carried out over the current range of 5–1000 mA within 20 min duration. Platinum foil was cleaned after each experiment by reversing the current flow in a cell and then dipping the same in 10% HCl (A.R.) for 1 min duration. All the experiments were performed at room temperature (30 ± 2°) under unstirred conditions. All the potentials are referred to a saturated calomel electrode.

SEM images of the electrodes before and after polarisation of the working electrode in a typical concentration of ammonium chloride were obtained by NEOL, JSM-35 scanning electron microscope.

Weight-loss method was adopted for the study of corrosion of the electrodes (1 cm² area) by immersing it in 5.5 *N* ammonium chloride solutions (10 ml) for a continuous period of 410 h in the absence of an impressed current. The corrosion products were removed by dipping the electrodes in 15% NH₄OH for 10 min. The corrosion rate was determined in mpy (mils penetration per year) using the formula, $mpy = 534 W/DAT$ where *W*, *D*, *A* and *T* have their usual significance.

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